

Title: "Wireless Electricity from the Gods: The Surprising Link Between Ancient Egypt, Nikola Tesla, and Modern Science"

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Introduction

Now more than ever, clean energy is crucial. As the world struggles with climate change and environmental degradation, finding sustainable ways to power our societies is crucial. However, clean energy has a fascinating millennia-old history. Humans have used nature's power to improve the world since the ancient Egyptians.

Clean energy was first recognized by Egyptians (Rannah, 2017a; Brakels, 2020). They built massive pyramids that generated electricity over 4,000 years ago. According to recent research, the pyramids were designed as giant power plants that harnessed the earth's natural energy to create a global electricity system (Sky, 2018; Kirkham, 2018). The Egyptians created a sustainable and renewable power source by using conductive materials and ion movement (Dobson, 2017).

Figure 1. Pyramid of Khufu, c. 2551–2528 B.C.E. (Calvert, 2023)

In the modern era, Nikola Tesla was another visionary inventor obsessed with clean energy. Tesla developed alternating current (AC) electricity as a Serbian-American scientist and engineer (Hungeski, 2010). Wireless electricity, a global system that would transmit power through the air without wires or cables, was his most revolutionary idea (Gaura & James Peter Brusey, 2021). Tesla envisioned a world where energy was free and unlimited, and everyone had access to clean, sustainable power.

Figure 2. Nikola Tesla (Mosher, 2017)

We will examine the ancient Egyptians' planetary electricity system and Nikola Tesla's wireless electricity system in the context of today's global challenges in this article. We'll examine the scientific principles behind these ideas and the pros and cons of large-scale implementation. By the end of this article, you'll understand clean energy's history and future and how innovative ideas can change the world.

Egyptian pyramids and planetary electricity:

Humanity's most impressive structures are the ancient Egyptian pyramids. Archaeologists and scientists are still puzzled by these massive monuments, built over 4,000 years ago. The pyramids were built as pharaohs' tombs, but some researchers believe they generated electricity (Sky, 2018; Kirkham, 2018).

This theory holds that the pyramids were giant power plants that harnessed earth energy to power the planet (Edwards, 2016). This system works by moving ions, electrically charged particles in the earth's atmosphere. By strategically placing copper, gold, and silver around the pyramid, the ancient Egyptians created a sustainable and renewable power source (Brakels, 2020).

Figure 3. The Great Pyramid of Khufu as a DC Power Generator: There is evidence that the Great Pyramid generated power. It likely used refined metals in the King's and Queen's chambers to create a large galvanic cell with copper as the anode and gold as the cathode, generating and storing DC electricity. (Herman, 2021)

Some researchers believe that the pyramids stored and released energy like giant capacitors (Rannah, 2017b). Some believe the pyramids were aligned with astronomical events like planet positions and sun and moon cycles to regulate energy flow (McIlroy, 2000; Katz, 2018). The idea of using earth energy to generate electricity is intriguing and raises questions about ancient civilizations' ingenuity and creativity.

Figure 4. Khufu's "Relieving Chamber" Air Electrical Capacitor: The "Chambers of Construction" or "Relieving Chamber" is a massive, multilayered air capacitor that stores electrons using granite and air's different dielectric properties. Inductive negative charge accumulated in the air space between the granite beams and the positively charged, grounded limestone bulk of the tomb. The capacitor's granite beams are physically connected to the King's sarcophagus, which holds the gold cathode and attracts negative electrons. (Herman, 2021)

In summary, the ancient Egyptians' planetary electricity system is intriguing and challenges our assumptions about clean energy history. The Egyptians created a sustainable and renewable power source by using King's conductive materials and ion movement. While the pyramid power plant theory is controversial (Wikipedia Contributors, 2023), it reminds us that the search for clean

energy is not new, and that human ingenuity has always been driven by the desire to improve the world.

Nikola Tesla and wireless electricity:

Nikola Tesla was a brilliant modern scientist and inventor. Tesla, who was born in Serbia in 1856, immigrated to the US in the 1880s and pioneered AC electricity. Tesla's most ambitious and revolutionary idea was wireless electricity, a global system that would transmit power without wires or cables (Gaura & James Peter Brusey, 2021; Natalie, 2021).

Figure 5. *Tesla's Wireless Electricity* (Nikola Tesla – World Famous Inventor - Srpsko Narodno Vijeće - SNV, 2020)

Tesla believed wireless electricity could give everyone free, unlimited energy. He wanted to use resonant frequencies and electromagnetic waves to build a network of towers to transmit electrical energy through the air. Tesla believed that tuning the towers to the same frequency would create a resonant system that would amplify power and allow it to be transmitted over long distances (Randles,2023).

Electromagnetic waves are the scientific foundation of wireless electricity (Charles The Scientist, 2023; Ma, 2018). These energy waves travel at the speed of light and are created by charged particles. Resonant circuits made from special coils and capacitors can amplify these waves and transmit them over long distances without wires or cables (Lin & Ziolkowski, 2020; Jiang et al., 2017a, 2017b; Shan et al., 2022). A global wireless electricity system could reduce carbon emissions and provide energy to remote areas, but the technology is still being developed.

Figure 6. Block diagram wireless power transfer by using solar energy (Fareq et al., 2014)

To recapitulate, Nikola Tesla's vision of a global wireless electricity system shows human creativity and imagination. Tesla believed he could create a sustainable, renewable power source for everyone by using resonant frequencies and electromagnetic waves. Tesla's legacy continues to inspire inventors and scientists around the world, and this system's potential benefits for clean energy are enormous.

The relevance of planetary and wireless electricity today:

Today's world needs planetary and wireless electricity. In the face of climate change, energy poverty, and clean energy access, innovative and sustainable energy solutions are needed. Planetary and wireless electricity systems may solve these issues, but their implementation has pros and cons.

Planetary and wireless electricity can reduce energy poverty and provide clean energy to remote and underserved areas (Georgieva, 2015). Lack of energy hinders development and progress for many people worldwide. Planetary and wireless electricity systems can help overcome this barrier by providing a renewable, sustainable, and universal power source.

On the other hand, implementing planetary and wireless electricity systems is difficult. Technically, these systems need advances in materials science, engineering, and physics. They also require a large infrastructure that can be costly to build and maintain. From an economic and social perspective, planetary and wireless electricity systems may face resistance from established energy interests and require significant changes to how we think about and use energy (Mor, 2022; Kiani et al., 2023).

In a nutshell, planetary and wireless electricity could solve today's energy problems. These systems provide clean, renewable energy to everyone. However, their implementation will require significant advances in science, engineering, and infrastructure development. The future of clean energy depends on our ability to overcome these challenges and embrace innovative and sustainable energy solutions.

Conclusion:

From the ancient Egyptians' planetary electricity system to Nikola Tesla's wireless electricity system, this article has covered the fascinating history and future of clean energy. We have seen how innovative energy ideas can transform our world and help us address climate change, energy poverty, and access to clean energy.

As we look to the future, it's more important than ever to explore and develop innovative energy ideas. Clean energy can help us build a sustainable and fair world for future generations.

There are many resources for learning about clean energy and supporting the transition to a sustainable energy future. From online courses and educational programs to advocacy groups and local initiatives, there are many ways to get involved and make a difference. We can create a

world where clean energy is the norm, and everyone has access to a brighter, more sustainable future by working together and embracing innovation.

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